

**PRIMARY TO EDUCATION PASSING IN CHILDREN NATURE WITH
INTRODUCTION IN THE PROCESS STRUCTURE OF ARGUMENTATIVE
REASONING SKILLS.**

**Turayev Yolkin Sherzod ugli,
against state university teacher.**

Yolkinturayev@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

Get started to education passing children's argumentative reasoning skills is a very complex psychological education, which includes the speech mechanisms of programming, planning, implementation and control of a speech statement. In addition, the structure and content of evidence-based reasoning skills of children of primary school age are directly related to the structure of the argument (conjecture, evidence, conclusion). directed.

KEY WORDS: primary education, evidence-based reasoning, complex psychological education, speech statement, programming, planning, implementation, control, speech mechanisms, structure and content of the skill of evidence-based reasoning, assumption, evidence, conclusion.

The following qualitative features of evidence-based reasoning skills in children of primary school age can be distinguished:

1. Goal orientation, which is manifested as the child's ability to control speech activity in order to form a substantiated statement or its parts in accordance with the idea plan. Goal orientation describes the child's ability to determine the topic of the statement, to maintain it in the process of communication with the interlocutor, to include evidence in everyday speech life in accordance with its functional purpose. At the same time, the content, logicity, emotionality, validity and reliability of the evidence are evaluated.

2. The dynamism that reflects the ability of children of primary school age to quickly find the necessary arguments and ways of expressing them. The dynamism is reflected in the speed of the evidenced speech movement and its flexibility.

3. Integrativeness: Verbal and non-verbal skills, communicative skills, speech etiquette skills, etc. are combined from the argumentative skills of children of primary school age. The integrative nature of evidence-based reasoning skills in children is manifested in the inclusion of elements of telling, explaining, reasoning. Reasoning skills, because of their integrative nature, represent a system of skills of different order and description.

4. Evidence-based reasoning skills of primary school children in various genres of speech communication, with or without the help of a pedagogue-educator, with or without visual support, which is manifested in independence.

The analysis of psychological-pedagogical literature makes it possible to emphasize the lack of research on the problem of formation of evidence-based reasoning skills in the process of introduction to nature in childhood of primary school age. Only some studies focus on the content that helps to achieve the stated goal. For example, in some scientific studies, the tasks of forming argumentation skills are emphasized, which are manifested in the ability to ask, explain, accept or reject someone's opinion. After targeted education, children entering primary education will be able not only to understand the term "reasoning", to see the specific features of this type of statement, but also to be able to express them in their own speech. will be done. Peculiarities of the formation of speech-reasoning in children of primary school age have been studied. Difficulties faced by children of primary school age in forming reasoning are noted, such as: difficulties in expressing cause-and-effect relationships in words; non-compliance with the given algorithm; lack of content, brevity and divisions in statements; replacement of other types of statements (describing, telling), etc. In assessing and analyzing the level of development of research activity of children

of primary school age, the children's answers are poorly grounded in making assumptions and drawing conclusions.

The brief description of the above-mentioned studies, which reflect only the theoretical and pedagogical aspects of the problem of the formation of evidence-based reasoning skills in children of primary school age, also indicates the importance of the problem under study and the need to find effective tools that help to implement this process.

Having considered the essence and content of the concept of "evidential reasoning skills" in children of primary school age, it can be assumed that the mechanism of their formation in the communicative and research activities of children of general secondary schools are established as detailed types of activities carried out in the educational process of elementary school students. The modern educational process of general secondary schools should be developed on the basis of research, in which the child becomes a discoverer and experimenter. Technologies of logical-mathematical development, visual activity, fiction, etc., have such opportunities for the manifestation of research behavior in children. But nature is the main and natural means of learning about the world, expressing it in words, and, accordingly, forming evidence-based reasoning skills in children of primary school age. It is no coincidence that nature has served as a source of education and development at all times and in all nations. It is nature and its activity that allowed man to make wonderful discoveries in science, art, and culture.

Structural structure of evidence-based reasoning skills in children of primary school age

Skills	Components
Guess or talk express get skill	The ability to identify a topic and maintain it in the process of argumentative reasoning
	The ability to express an assumption in a manner appropriate to the communication situation

	The ability to incorporate an argument into an evidence-based text
	Ability to choose and implement speech tools
Selection of evidence and methods of proof of assumption done increase get skill	The ability to distinguish signs that are important to prove a previous hypothesis
	The ability to select and advance arguments appropriate to the communication situation
	The ability to include arguments in the text
	The ability to choose verbal and non-verbal means to convince the interlocutor according to the communication situation
	The ability to express agreement or disagreement with the interlocutor's opinion through "I think you are not right...", "I disagree with your opinion...".
In conclusion proof based on thoughts bring get skill	The ability to express conclusions - summarizing
	The ability to connect the conclusion with the main assumption
	Ability to use speech tool in assessment
	The ability to choose a language tool that helps to draw conclusions
	The ability to evaluate the opinions of peers based on evidence

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